

Identification of core elements for a machine-actionable Data Management Plan metadata schema in the NFDI

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Abstract:

The interoperability of data management plans (DMPs) across platforms and application profiles plays a key role in the implementation of good scientific practice and of the FAIR data principles. The application profile for "machine-actionable DMPs" published by the Research Data Alliance (RDA) marks an important step in this direction. More recently, networking initiatives such as the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) are collecting and generating templates for DMPs based on the needs of different subject-related communities and implemented in different DMP software tools. In a two-day hackathon we analyzed the RDA maDMP application profile, discussed the meaning and applicability of the proposed elements and aligned them to selected community-driven schemas and platforms for DMPs and for metadata. The results are available in the form of crosswalks and are intended to pave the way towards an maDMP based

on schema.org to improve information exchange between DMP platforms and other research data services, and alignment between DMPs and Software Management Plans.

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Introduction

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are becoming a must across scientific disciplines and a tool for researchers and funding bodies to promote and favour better research, as they support a better organization and preservation of research data. DMPs are associated to short-term (projects) or long-term research activities and are created and maintained by researchers based on DMP templates, i. e., collections of questions that will help researchers manage their data from beginning to end, sometimes open-ended when datasets are maintained, updated, and released either on a regular basis (i.e., scheduled releases) or as needed. DMP templates can serve as practical checklists to help researchers consider key actions for managing and sharing their data. They are also increasingly mandated by funders to ensure that essential information is captured to support good research practices throughout the data lifecycle, enabling data to remain accessible and potentially reusable beyond the original project.

Similarly to DMPs, other forms of "output management plans" for different research outputs are being established. In particular, software management plans (SMPs) help formalize a set of structures and goals that ensure accessibility and reusability of self-developed research software in the short, medium and long term. Despite being not so widely accepted as DMPs, SMPs rely on a much longer tradition for structured and automated documentation.

Although useful for humans, DMPs and SMPs as free-text documents cannot be easily interpreted by a machine to create logical connections between datasets and other related objects such as actors (e.g., creators of a dataset, funders) and other research outputs (e.g., initial data used as input, software used to process the data). To make such connections visible in a machine-processable way, the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\) DMP Common Standards Working Group](#) proposed a [machine-actionable DMP](#) (RDA maDMP) in the form of an application profile, i.e., a metadata schema collecting information in a structured and harmonised way not relating on any particular vocabulary, serialisation or implementation workflow, which allows for "automatic exchange, integration, and validation of information provided in DMPs and facilitating the exchange of information between systems acting on behalf of stakeholders involved in the research life cycle" [1].

Metadata recorded to such an application profile can be easily exported to a text-based document, since they contain the same information, but allow for broader usage possibilities because of the higher granularity and possibility for automation. To improve the acceptance among researchers and reduce barriers, maDMP-compatible metadata should be supported by

DMP platforms such as the [Research Data Management Organiser \(RDMO\)](#) [2] or [DataPlan](#) [3]. However, to make maDMPs an effective tool supporting interoperability and reusability, there is a need for some core agreements at metadata level, so different DMP hosting platforms can easily exchange information. Based on this RDA proposal, we analyzed their proposed application profile within the scope of the German National Research Data Infrastructures (NFDI) initiative, with two primary goals:

- first, we wanted to understand commonalities and differences across the DMP-related needs expressed by different NFDI consortia while also aligning these findings with global efforts to integrate NFDI activities into the broader international research landscape;
- second, based on commonalities, we wanted to propose an initial draft for a minimal set of core metadata elements that could later be adopted and extended by the NFDI communities according to their own needs.

Besides the effort from RDA maDMPs, another blueprint for the present work was the recently published machine-actionable layer for Software Management Plans (maSMP) [4], developed in a joint effort by NFDI4DataScience and ELIXIR (through the Focus Group on Software Best Practices) and coordinated by ZB MED. This machine-actionable layer is based on previous work [5], [6], [7] and has been built as an extension to schema.org. Following Bioschemas [8] practices, the ZB MED maSMP vocabulary provides types [4] covering information needs from SMPs as well as profiles [9], i.e., recommendations of use. The maSMP has been adopted by the ELIXIR Software Management Wizard [10] and it is planned to be integrated into RDMO as part of the [DMP4NFDI project](#). Ultimate aim of the present work is to build a similar framework for machine-actionable DMPs.

Methods

To achieve our goals, we met in person during three days to work together in a hackathon style, i.e., involving active participation from all attendees, self-organized in small groups based on common interests or domains, followed by elaborations from each perspective and discussions towards common agreements across all participants. Our hackathon counted with participation of 19 people from 13 institutions, nine NFDI consortia (DataPLANT, FAIRagro, MaRDI, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4DataScience, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Ing, NFDIxCS, PUNCH), two Base4NFDI projects (DMP4NFDI and PID4NFDI) and a guided tour of two tools supporting the creation and follow up of DMPs (DataPLAN and RDMO).

Analysis of the maDMP schema and preselection of clusters

As preliminary work, we had a discussion to select the primary concepts to build our maDMP architecture around. We took the RDA maDMP application profile as a starting point, the diagram corresponding to its logical structure is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of maDMP concepts used within the application profile proposed by RDA DMP Common Standards WG (taken from [11])

The RDA maD[12]MP schema organizes information in 93 fields, organized in a tree structure stemming from a root node called `DMP` and clustered around a small number of main secondary nodes. Among these, the following were initially acknowledged to be relevant: `Project`, `Dataset`, and `Distribution`. Elements related to people or organizations (`Contact` and `Contributor`), and to `License` were left aside, as there is already some consensus regarding the minimum metadata required in those cases as they are commonly used in traditional scholarly publications. `Security_and_privacy`, `Technical_Resource`, and `Metadata` were left aside due to lack of clarity in the documentation provided for these elements in the RDA maDMP. `Cost` was mostly discussed as highly relevant to research projects, but not necessarily associated directly to a DMP but to the whole project.. `Host` was initially included as there were some participants from DMP (and DMP templates) hosting platforms. An additional element considered in our work was `OutputManagementPlan`, a common parent to DMP and software management plans (SMP). `OutputManagementPlan` is not present in the RDA maDMP, but it is included in the DataCite metadata mode [v4.5](#) [12], and used in the maSMPs created by ZB MED [4].

Determination of commonalities and differences: Crosswalks

The following task was the comparison of the maDMP schema with the needs and developments presented by the different NFDI consortia. This was performed by creating *crosswalks*. A crosswalk is a grid to present and highlight commonalities and differences among two or more different ways of representing information (e.g., schemas or ontologies), usually expressed aligning (mapping) all other schemas against one chosen as a reference. A crosswalk can be presented as a spreadsheet, with sheets corresponding to main concepts (classes or types); rows corresponding to their attributes (object properties or datatype

properties); and columns containing metainformation – such as label, range, description, cardinality (one, many), requirement level (minimum, recommended, optional), usage examples – first for the reference and then for any other schema to be compared.

For the present work, the organizers provided crosswalk templates centered around the clusters identified previously: `OutputManagementPlan`, `DMP`, `Project`, `Dataset`, `Distribution`, and `Host`. The crosswalk templates (and results) are publicly available [13].

We proceeded with creating crosswalks, by comparing and mapping the RDA maDMP schema to metadata schemas (e.g., schema.org), DMP platforms (e.g., RDMO, DataPlant), and DMP schemas (e.g., DFG Checklist). A number of schemas was initially proposed for comparison (see Table 1); a first prioritization led to the selection of nine schemas, which were tested for alignment with the RDA-maDMP schema in small small groups (2-3 participants).

Table 1. List of DMP-related schemas, indicating which ones were selected for a crosswalk

Resource	Link	Selected
DataPLAN	https://plan.nfdi4plants.org/	Yes
DataCite metadata schema v4.5	https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.5/	Yes
DMPT GFBio (NFDI4Biodiversity)	https://dmp.gfbio.org/	Yes
DFG Checklist (RDMO)	https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/master/rdmo2.x/rdmorganiser/questions/questions-DFG-Checkliste.xml	Yes
Horizon Europe (RDMO)	https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/master/rdmo2.x/rdmorganiser/questions/questions-horizon-europe.xml	Yes
RDMO	https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/blob/master/rdmo2.x/rdmorganiser/domain/attributes.xml	Yes
Metadata4Ing	https://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing/	Yes
Schema.org	https://schema.org/	Yes
Other reference formats NFDIxCS	https://nfdixcs.org/	Yes
CodeMeta	https://codemeta.github.io/terms/	No
DCat	https://www.w3.org/ns/dcat	No
PROV	http://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/	No
RAiD - Research Activity Identifier	https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/	No
Core Dataset Research (KDSF)	https://kerndatensatz-forschung.de/index.php?id=spezifikation_de-DE	No
VIVO	https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/VIVODOC111x/Ontology+Reference	No
Research Data Management Container (RDMC)	https://nfdixcs.pages.uni-potsdam.de/rdmc-architecture/#research-data-management-container-rdmc	No
Croissant ML	https://docs.mlcommons.org/croissant/docs/croissant-spec.html	No
Citation File Format (CFF)	https://citation-file-format.github.io/	No
Other reference formats (Zotero,		No

RIS, BibTeX)		
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The individual crosswalks were manually merged to present them as a consolidated dataset and deposited in Zenodo as a dataset [13].

Design of a core maDMP schema

In a subsequent phase, the participants defined a draft metadata schema from scratch or based on their previous experience, working in larger groups (6-7 participants). Our discussion focussed on the field clusters "DMP", "Dataset" and "Project", trying to generate a systematic overview of the fields belonging to these three concepts taking into account what had been defined in previous efforts (e.g., maDMP application profile, maSMP metadata schema). Working in larger groups (6–7 participants), they drew on both their domain experience and previous efforts, such as the RDA maDMP application profile and the maSMP metadata schema, to define a draft metadata schema grounded in shared understanding and practical needs.

Results

Crosswalks

With regards to the main elements considered by the RDA maDMP application profile, `Host` and `ManagementPlan` were excluded from the created crosswalks (although initially included in the crosswalk template). `ManagementPlan` was not included mostly due to time constraints, as this would require a careful look into DMP templates used by different platforms and stakeholders (e.g., funders). With regards to `Host`, it was a general consensus that the information concerning the hosting platform does not fall under the responsibility of the author of a DMP but should rather be curated by the host itself and just referenced within a DMP. `Cost` was found to be indeed more related to the project than to the DMP. `Distribution` was also discussed, and the participants found that this does not necessarily have to be an element on its own but an attribute of `Dataset` (e.g., as a link to a downloadable file); only whenever more information is needed (e.g., size, format) `Distribution` could be an element on its own. All crosswalks are publicly available [13]. In summary, the crosswalks focused on DMP, Dataset, Project and Distribution as follows:

Schema \ Cluster	Management Plan	DMP	Project	Dataset	Distribution	Host
DMPT GFBio (NFDI4Biodiversity)	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
DataPLAN	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No

DataCite metadata schema v4.5	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
Horizon Europe (RDMO)	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
DFG Checklist (RDMO)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Other reference formats NFDIxCS	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
RDMO	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Metadata4Ing	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Schema.org	No	No	Yes	No	No	No

In the following subsections, we provide more information on the crosswalks, indicating how many resources provided information, out of the total participating in a given crosswalk. For instance “(6/7) `contact`” would indicate that six resources out of seven filled in some information corresponding to the property `contact` (e.g., for the case of DMPs).

Crosswalks for DMP

As expected, the cluster `DMP` was covered by all schemas centered on data management plans (RDMO, DataPLAN, GFBio, NFDIxCS, Horizon Europe, DFG Checklist) as well as by DataCite.

- Property, range, description, cardinality, requirement (minimum, recommended, optional):
 - (6/7) `contact` was mapped for all cases except Horizon Europe, in all cases it corresponded to a person. Mostly, having only one contact was preferred (except for DFG Checklist) and it was judged as a minimum property (except for DataCite where `contactPerson` under contributor roles is recommended).
 - (5/7) `contributor` was mapped for most resources, with the exception of RDMO and NFDIxCS. Contributors correspond to multiple persons, provided on an optional basis (except for DataCite where it is recommended). The amount of information provided varies from one resource to the other: in the case of Horizon Europe and DFG Checklist a string (i.e., person's name) is enough while DataCite also expects an affiliation and identifier, while GFBio an e-mail address.
 - (4/7) `cost` was mapped for DataPLAN, Horizon Europe, DFG Checklist, and GFBio. Same as the RDA maDMP reference point, GFBio accepts multiple costs as optional while DFG Checklist has them as required. Horizon Europe includes different kinds of costs, e.g, personnel, non-personnel, so it is more granular than what it is currently considered in RDA maDMP. Horizon Europe granularity could be sorted out with an additional attribute indicating the kind of cost.
 - (5/7) `created` was mapped by most sources except for NFDIxCS and DFG Checklist. All coincide that only one “creation” date should be provided. DataCite

uses recommended rather than minimum as done by Horizon Europe. The other sources did not provide information about cardinality and requirement level.

- (5/7) `dataset` was mapped by most sources except for RDMO and DFG Checklist. All agree that at least one Dataset should be provided. As requirement level, DataCite uses recommended, GFBio does not provide information, and the others agree on minimum.
- (3/7) `description` is reported by DataPLAN, DataCite and GFBio. DataCite and GFBio accept many descriptions, the former as recommended, the latter as minimum.
- (2/7) `ethical_issues_description`, `ethical_issues_exist`, and `ethical_issues_report`. These three elements are present in DataPLAN. DataCite could use `description` to include `ethical_issues_description` (however the intention is not quite the same) and `datacite:relatedIdentifiers` to link to the `ethical_issues_report` (but the nature is not fully captured).
- (3/7) `dmp_id` is reported by DataPLAN, DataCite and GFBio. DataCite requires this property as minimum (mandatory as called in DataCite) while the others do not report the requirement level.
- (3/7) `language` is reported by DataPLAN, DataCite and GFBio. DataCite requires this property as recommended and accepts only one value. The others do not provide further information.
- (4/7) `modified` is reported by NFDIxCS, DataPLAN, DataCite and GFBio. NFDIxCS and DataCite coincide on having it as minimum and only one value. The others do not provide further information.
- (4/7) `project` was mapped for RDMO, DataPLAN, DataCite and GFBio. Both DataCite and GFBio accept many projects but DataCite has it as recommended while GFBio as minimum.
- (3/7) `title` was mapped for DataPLAN, DataCite and GFBio. Both DataCite and GFBio would accept only one title as minimum.
- Additional properties identified in the analyzed resources:
 - DataPLAN also includes `replace` and `checkbox`, no further information is provided to understand these additional properties.
 - NFDIxCS listed version of the DMP, and two more properties that are copied from the Datasets referred to from the DMP: whether any personal data is included and a list of security and privacy issues.
 - DataCite mandates some additional properties: `creator` (cardinality = many), `publisher` (cardinality = one), `publication_year` (one) and `resource_type` (cardinality = one) with value = `datacite:OutputManagementPlan`, which might be made more precise defining specific types. Funding references are also included as optional with multiple values.
 - GFBio and DataCite also include funding information. It also has a `category` with domain-specific values (Algae & Protists; Bacteriology,Virology; Ecology & Environment; Geoscience; Microbiology; Mycology; Paleontology; Zoology;

Other), `reproducible` (whether or not the data is reproducible), and `policies_or_guidelines`. These three properties accept multiple optional values.

- Recommended vocabularies: no information provided, but DataCite prescribes an object schema for the range of some fields, such as contributor (it should be an object of the class `Person` with name, identifier, e-mail address).
- Comments: mostly not used, only for the crosswalks to the DFG Checklist (mostly to indicate the lack of semantic equivalence as DFG Checklist uses strings for any required property) and Horizon Europe (where additional information is required in some cases, for instance, there are multiple responsibility levels/actors). In some cases, for instance DataCite, a comment was used to indicate the expected format for dates.

Comments to DMP

Only NFDIxCS provided comments for DMP as specified in the RDA maDMP application profile. While RDA maDMP considers only a person as a possible `contact`, NFDIxCS would add organizations as well. In the case of `contributor`, adding roles from a list of options would be also desirable. In addition to `dataset`, a link to the dataset documentation could be useful (note: that one could also be specified at the `dd` level). Similarly, the `modified` date could be complemented with the names of those responsible from the latest modification.

Crosswalks for Project

The crosswalks for `Project` were provided for five resources: RDMO, Metadata4Ing, NFDIxCS, Schema.org, and the DFG Checklist. `ResearchProject` exists as a type in Schema.org where all the properties proposed in the RDA maDMP are also covered plus some additional ones.

- Property, range, description, cardinality, requirement (*minimum*, recommended, optional):
 - (1/5) `description` Schema.org includes this property for `Project`, suggested in the crosswalk as one and minimum.
 - (2/5) `end` property is considered by Metadata4Ing (namely `endOfProject`) and Schema.org (namely `endDate`).
 - (2/5) `funding`, including funder, funding status and grant identifier, is partially considered by Metadata4Ing (funder only) and fully covered by Schema.org.
 - (2/5) `start` is considered by Metadata4Ing (namely `startOfProject`) and Schema.org (namely `startDate`).
 - (3/5) `title` is also included in RDMO and Schema.org. For the DFG Checklist, the project title is not considered as the checklist is part of a project description, so the project title is found at a different level.
- Additional properties identified in the analyzed resources: Metadata4Ing also considers a project identifier (`projectReferenceID`) and participants (`projectParticipant`, either persons or organizations). NFDIxCS also includes a research domain.

Schema.org offers many more options as ResearchProject is a type, see <https://schema.org/ResearchProject>.

Crosswalks for Dataset

The crosswalks for Dataset were provided by RDMO, DataPLAN, Metadata4Ing, NFDIxCS, Horizon Europe, DFG Checklist, and DataCite.

- Property, range, description, cardinality, requirement (minimum, recommended, optional):
 - (3/7) `data_quality_assurance` was mapped on RDMO, DFG and DataCite.
 - (2/7) `dataset_id` was mapped on RDMO and DataCite.
 - (3/7) `description` was mapped on RDMO, Horizon Europe RDMO and DataCite.
 - (3/7) `distribution` was mapped on RDMO, Metadata4Ing and DataCite.
 - (2/7) `issued` was mapped on RDMO and DataCite.
 - (2/7) `keyword` was mapped on RDMO and DataCite.
 - (1/7) `language` was mapped on DataCite.
 - (3/7) `metadata` was mapped on RDMO, DFG and DataCite.
 - (1/7) `personal_data` was mapped on RDMO.
 - (1/7) `preservation_statement` was mapped on RDMO.
 - (3/7) `security_and_privacy` was mapped on RDMO, DFG and DataCite.
 - (2/7) `technical_resource` was mapped on RDMO and DataCite.
 - (3/7) `title` was mapped on RDMO, DFG and DataCite.
 - (1/7) `type` was mapped on DataCite.
- Additional properties identified in the analyzed resources: DataCite suggest adding creator, contact person, publisher, publication year, version, size and format. NFDIxCS suggest adding ethical issues, version, linked dataset, end date. RDMO suggest adding: documentation, infrastructure, creator name,
- Recommended vocabularies: DataCite suggests to use DOI for `dataset_id`. No specific vocabulary was recommended except normal boolean values and Dates
- Comment: DataPLAN did not have a specific dataset section because it uses the Investigation, Study, Assay (ISA) [14] format for dataset metadata.

Comments for Dataset

Only NFDIxCS provided comments for Dataset. NFDIxCS would require more detailed information about the quality so rather than a text, a link to an external document would be more appropriate. In addition to security and privacy issues, ethical aspects should also be included. The machine-actionability of simple text is something that would require further assessment.

Crosswalks for Distribution

The crosswalks for `Distribution` were only provided by RDMO and Metadata4Ing.

- Property, range, description, cardinality, requirement (minimum, recommended, optional):
 - (2/2) `access_url` was mapped by RDMO (where it could be the same URL as the one used for `Dataset`) and Metadata4Ing (where multiple distribution options are considered).
 - (0/2) `available_until` is not covered.
 - (2/2) `byte_size` was mapped by RDMO (where an estimation would be acceptable) and Metadata4Ing (where the size is specified in bytes).
 - (1/2) `data_access` is named as `sharing` in RDMO with yes/no values. In RDMO, this property is complemented by the conditions of sharing (closer to `data_access` in RDA maDMP but expressed in text rather than as an enumerated list).
 - (0/2) `description` is not covered.
 - (1/2) `download_url` is also considered by Metadata4Ing.
 - (2/2) `format` in the RDA maDMP can be a media type as defined by the [Internet Assigned Numbers Authority \(IANA\)](#) but, if no good match there, free-text is also allowed. For Metadata4Ing it is only a media type while for RDMO is a text.
 - (1/2) `host` is mapped to `repository` in RDMO. Metadata4Ing also considered the packaging format and the compress format.
 - (1/2) `license` is not considered in RDMO but partially covered by the combination of conditions of access and the indication of an embargo period.
 - (0/2) `title` is not covered.

Draft of a core maDMP schema for NFDI

Using the RDA maDMP application profile and the schema.org extension proposed by the maSMP metadata schema, we created a draft for an NFDI core maDMP schema based on the crosswalks and discussions, represented as a diagram in Figure 2.

The elements (classes and properties) of this data model come from different origins. A large fraction comes directly from schema.org. Most elements from RDA maDMP have been included; many of them (.....) have a partial match to schema.org elements, thus fitting naturally into its semantic description, while others (`Cost`, `Security_and_Privacy`, and `Metadata`) have not been identified (yet). `Host` has been left aside on purpose for the reasons discussed previously; from a DMP perspective, a link to the hosting platform would be enough (`archiveAt` or `publisher` in schema.org could be used for such a purpose). `Technical_Resource` is also left aside in favor of a more specific option, such as the link to the software used to process datasets. The differences with

Figure 2. Types considered for an initial set of metadata elements for NFDI DMPs as an extension of schema.org. Thick lines represent those elements present in the RDA maDMP; red background represents elements coming from schema.org; purple the ones from maSMP; blue the new ones proposed in this work.

Our draft schema consists of the following types in this ordering/hierarchy:

- Thing
 - Action
 - SoftwareRunAction
 - CreativeWork
 - Dataset
 - MediaObject
 - DataDownload
 - SoftwareSourceCode
 - SoftwareApplication
 - maSMP:OutputManagementPlan
 - maSMP:SoftwareManagementPlan
 - dmp4nfdi:DMP

- Intangible
 - Grant
- Organization
 - Project
 - ResearchProject
- Person

Based on our discussions and findings, we submitted a change request to the RDA DMP common standards working group, hoping to contribute to adapt their application profile to praxis-near requirements. The differences between our proposal and the RDA maDMP profile were submitted as change requests for further discussion: <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard/issues/77>, <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard/issues/88>, <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard/issues/90>

Discussion

RDA maDMP application profile

In general, we agreed to the maDMP proposed by RDA; however, some types and links needed to be clarified for the purpose of a core set of elements for NFDI. In particular, three main points would differ from the RDA maDMP: (i) we found that `costs` would commonly be associated with a research project rather than with a DMP; (ii) although in the RDA maDMP `dataset` and `distribution` are defined as separate objects, many times this seems redundant, as a dataset is distributed directly via a download link; and finally, (iii) although we recognized the importance of metadata about the hosting platform (e.g., data repository, archive), we see the responsibility of providing and curating such information in the hands of the hosting platforms themselves or some resource registry, and not on the DMP authors, as remarked before.

Currently, the RDA model requires the existence of at least one dataset, which is supposed to have mandatory metadata which only existing real-world datasets will have. This model does not allow a maDMP to describe intended datasets to be created in the future, which is the most likely condition during the inception phase of a project. Making the current mandatory fields (ID, URLs, etc) optional would make the model more flexible.

Another point of discussion was regarding the actual text in a DMP document. As it is currently modelled in the RDA maDMP application profile, not much information about the actual content (i.e., questions and answers) is included. Rather, the focus lies on the involved actors (contact, contributors), costs, and datasets managed by the DMP. In this sense, the narrative of key decisions at key points during the research data lifecycle is lost (e.g., open or restrictive licenses, preservation channels). Furthermore, a DMP can change over time, and without any reference to the actual content it would be difficult to quickly compare changes.

The discussion also identified a possible related document type, namely data management guideline (or policy), which can be seen as a collection of long-term data-related decisions released by funders, research institutes, partnerships, subject-specific regulating bodies or single workgroups. Guidelines are not tight to a project, but obligate all members of research activities or research projects to a commitment towards good practices for research. Although a new type could be created for this purpose, the purpose and use are quite close to a DMP, and the current shape of the DMP type with the inclusion of questions and answers (as proposed by ZB MED in their maSMP) would also work for this use case. Therefore, we decided to also use the DMP type for this use case.

An issue difficult to directly represent with metadata corresponds to changes as the project progresses. For instance, at the beginning of a project the nature of the input data could have been identified but not necessarily a specific dataset. Similarly, there would be no software source code yet but a clear need and purpose to create one. Such changes are better captured with variations of the metadata (together with versioning), showing how more elements become available as the project advances.

In addition, research artifacts require some common information that is not yet well covered by schema.org. For instance, identification of the scientific domain; intended use; licensing; versioning; ethical, legal, and social aspects. Ethical aspects are already considered in the maSMP metadata schema, which could have a similar purpose as the Security_and_Privacy in the RDA maDMP. Still, more work is needed in that area.

Finally, while having a text-based machine-actionability is already a step forward, there is a need to move towards a more semantic representation as this could serve better areas such as explainability in Artificial Intelligence, where Knowledge Graphs (naturally emerging from machine-actionable metadata) are already being used for this purpose.

Machine-actionability

The discussion also touched / formalized the logical dependence between the terms “machine-readability”, “machine-processability”, and “machine-actionability”. Clearly, for a machine to take action on a particular description of a topic, it needs to be able to read the description and process it. Regarding the properties of the description, readability is a necessary condition. For this reason, we argue that the terms can be used interchangeably in agreement with others [15].

We then focused on the understanding of machine-actionability of digital objects among the participants, and we identified three levels, inspired by the Linked Data five stars model [16] and the FAIR data principles [17]:

- Level 1 = basic machine-actionability: information is structured in standardised metadata fields designated by univocal persistent identifiers, with no strict validation of the fields values/contents (free text).

- Level 2 = operational machine-actionability: additionally to Level 1, operations (e.g., download, delete) are defined, depending on object types and formats (e.g., image, dataset). This situation is similar to the approach of the [FAIR Digital Object \(FDO\) Forum](#) [18], [19].
- Level 3 = enhanced machine-actionability: additionally to Level 2, the field names and field values are restricted to belong (as much as possible) to a controlled terminology (controlled vocabulary or ontology).

Conclusion

We analyzed commonalities and differences across different NFDI consortia and projects regarding DMP needs and developed a set of core metadata elements that could later be adopted and extended by the NFDI communities according to their own needs.

Our analysis compared different authoritative (RDA, DataCite), technics-based (DataPLAN, RDMO) and community-based (NFDI consortia) approaches for the machine-actionable representation of DMPs, considering a parallel development for SMPs and the big global (nonscientific) *de facto* standard [schema.org](#) [20]. We were successful in defining a set of metadata, with particular focus on project- and dataset-related information, which can be in principle easily integrated in most of the scenarios/profiles considered. We hope that our work will help the agreement on a standard which is both semantically sound and application-ready.

This work is the starting impulse of several activities around maDMPs, which will continue operating and keeping synchron with each other. In particular, the development of a metadata schema will be carried on as part of the NFDI Base project DMP4NFDI, with collaboration from other efforts in Germany. The metadata schema should facilitate exchange across platforms such as RDMO and DataPlant. There will also be a collaboration with the RDA maDMP group to keep compatibility with their application profile.

Based on the discussions from this hackathon, we submitted a change request to the RDA DMP common standards working group, hoping to contribute to adapt their application profile to praxis-near requirements. We will pursue the discussion with them, either bilaterally via DMP4NFDI or internally via our co-authors who are also members of the working group.

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